

BIOLOGIYA FANINI O`QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI O`RNI VA AHAMIYATI.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biologiya fani bilan bir qatorda barcha tabiiy fanlar tizimida innovatsion texnologiyalarning o`rni va samaradorligi keltirib o`tiladi. Hozirgi vaqtda ta`lim tizimiga yangicha usulda yondashish talab qilinayotgan bir vaqtda, ushbu usullardan samarali foydalana oladigan malakali pedagog kadrlarni tayyorlash lozimligi haqida ham so`z yuritiladi.

Kalit so`zlar: innovatsiya, interfaol, biologiya, tabiiy fanlar, usul, pedagog, malaka, dars, o`quvchi, ta`lim.

Bugungi kunda rivojlanayotgan umumiy o`rta ta`lim tizimida biologiya fani o`qituvchilarini tayyorlash muammosi ta`lim miqyosida dolzarb hisoblanadi. Biologiyaning rivojlanishi va uning yutuqlarini jamiyat hayotiga tatbiq etilmoqda. Binobarin, kollej-litseylarda biologik ta`limning ahamiyati tobora ortib bormoqda. Yosh mutaxassisni tayyorlash jarayonida o`quvchi o`qituvchining bevosita rahbarligida, ta`lim mazmuni, metodlari, vositalari va shakllari yordamida organik olamning qonuniyatlari, hodisa va voqealarning mohiyati, o`ziga xos xususiyatlarini o`rganadi va bilim, ko`nikma hamda malakalarni egallaydi. Bundan ko`rinib turibdiki, o`quvchilar uchun o`quv jarayoni bilish jarayoni, uning faoliyati esa bilish faoliyatidir. O`qituvchi ta`lim jarayonida o`quvchilarning bilish faoliyatini tashkil etadi, boshqaradi, nazorat qiladi, baholaydi va o`qitishdan ko`zda tutilgan ta`limiy, tarbiyaviy va rivojlantiruvchi maqsadlarni amalga oshirish orqali shaxsning har tomonlama rivojlanishiga zamin yaratadi. O`qituvchi uchun ta`lim jarayoni o`quvchilarning faoliyati bilan uzviy bog`langan va mazkur jarayonni tahlil qiladigan, umumlashtirib, tegishli hollarda o`zgartirishlar kiritadigan ish jarayoni, kasbiy pedagogik faoliyati sanaladi. Darsda o`quvchilarning bilish faoliyati va o`qituvchining pedagogik faoliyati bir-biriga uyg'un ravishda tashkil etilgandagina o`qitishdan ko`zda tutilgan maqsadlarga erishish mumkin. O`quvchilarning bilish faoliyatini tashkil etish va boshqarish dars strukturasi asosini tashkil etadi. Shu sababli bu masalani chuqurroq o`rganish maqsadga muvofiq. Litsey biologiyasi boshqa fanlarga o`xshamagan holda, tabiat hodisalarga tizimli va tarixiy yondashuv birligini bilim kuchini ko`rsatishga yordam beradi. Biologiya o`qitish jarayonida kollej-litsey o`quvchilarning dialekt tafakkurini rivojlantirish bilan birgalikda ularda organik

dunyoning ilmiy manzarasi, hayotning tarixiyligi va uning harakat tizimidagi o'rni, qarama-qarshi bilish usullari bilan ochib beriladi. Biologiya maktab-litsey tizimidagi tabiatshunoslik siklining yetakchi fanlardan biridir, chunki u shaxsning shakllanishida va rivojlanishida katta ahamiyatga ega.

Baliq skeleti metodi. Bu metod o'quvchilarda mavzu yuzasidan muayyan masala mohiyatini tasvirlash va yechish qobiliyatini shakllantiradi. Metodni qo'llashda o'quvchilarda mantiqiy fikrlash, mavzu mohiyatini yorituvchi tayanch tushuncha, ma'lumotlarni muayyan tizimga keltirish, ularni tahlil qilish ko'nikmalari rivojlanadi; 1) o'qituvchi o'quvchilarni metodni qo'llash sharti bilan tanishtiradi; 2) ular guruhlariga birlashtiriladilar; 3) guruhlar topshiriqlarni bajaradilar; 4) guruhlar o'z yechimlarini jamoaga taqdim etadilar; 5) jamoa guruhlar yechimlari yuzasidan muhokama uyushtiradi.

Keys-stadi» texnologiyasi. «Keys-stadi» (ingliz tiliga. «case»majmua, aniq vaziyat, «study» — ta'lim) texnologiyasi o'quvchilarda aniq , real yoki sun'iy yaratilgan muammoli vaziyatni tahlil qilish orqali eng maqbul variantlarini topish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Mazkur texnologiya o'quvchilarni bevosita har qanday mazmunga ega vaziyatni o'rganish va tahlil qilishga o'rgatadi. Texnologiyaning samaradorligi o'quv jarayonini quyidagi texnologik bosqichlarda tashkil etilishiga bog'liq: 1) keys yechimini topish bo'yicha individual ishlash; 2) keys yechimini topishda jamoaviy hamkorlikka erishish. Mazkur texnologiyani qo'llashda individual ishlashda quyidagi tartibda ish ko'riladi; 1) o'quvchining keys-stadi texnologiyasi mohiyati va undan foydalanish shartlari bilan tanishishi; 2) o'quvchi tomonidan taqdim etilgan muammoning o'rganilishi; 3) muammo yuzasidan asosiy va ikkinchi darajali masalalarni ajratish, shakllantirish va asoslash; 4) tadqiqot metodlarini tanlash va vaziyatni tahlil qilish; 5) taqdim etilgan muammoing amaliy jihatlarni o'rganish; 6) berilgan muammoni yechishning usul va vositalarini aniqlash; 7) taqdim etilgan yechimni ta'lim amaliyotiga tatbiq etish chora tadbirlarini belgilash. **Key-study** bo'yicha jamoaviy hamkorlik quyidagi tartibda amalga oshadi: 1. Muammo, uning yechimlari yuzasidan jamoa (guruh) a'zolari o'zaro fikr almashadilar; 2. Masalaning yechimi sifatida taqdim etilgan variantlar muhokama qilinib, ularning maqbullik darajasi baholanadi; 3. Muammoli vaziyatning yechimini ta'minlaydigan aniq dastur ishlab chiqiladi; 4. Masalaning yechimi to'g'risida ma'lumot beradigan taqdimot tayyorlanadi va unda namoyish etiladigan materiallar rasmiylashtiriladi. Bu kabi metodlar o'z mohiyatiga ko'ra tabiiy fanlar tizimida ta'lim oluvchilarda bilim olish faolligini oshirish, ularni kichik guruh va jamoada ishlash, o'rganilayotgan mavzu, muammolar bo'yicha

shaxsiy qarashlarini dadil, erkin ifodalash, o'z fikrlarini himoya qilish, dalillar bilan asoslash, tengdoshlarini tinglay olish, g'oyalarni yanada boyitish, bildirilgan mavjud mulohazalar orasidan eng maqbul yechimni tanlab olishga, rag'batlantirish imkoniyatiga egaligi bilan alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Xulosa qilib shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki, biologiya ta'limida yuqoridagi interfaol metodlardan foydalangan holda darslar tashkil etilsa, o'quvchilarning ilm olishlari, o'z mutaxassisliklari bo'yicha bilimlarini yanada oshirish mumkin.

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